

Crisis Management And Business Management: Effective Leadership and Decision-Making Processes in Times of Crisis

Dr. Pamir DIRIL¹

Göksel KARADENİZ²

To cite this article: Collaborate, Current Science, Volume 5, No. 5-10, 2024, p. 53– 80. - 0099-0001-2410-0203.

Our studies are in a format accredited, approved, and supported by EAALS - European Academic Studies and Laboratory Services. ("Scientific Studies -

Current Science Georgia") "EAALS offers all our works, services, and publications to the world scientists at the stage of carrying our control, accreditation, and support processes to the international platform." ("CURRENT SCIENCE")

("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

ISSN: 2667-9515

¹ **St. Clements University , Psychology Department Faculty Member , Orcid ID: 0000-0001-8913-343X, Mail : academician1970@hotmail.com**

² **St. Clements University , PhD in Business Management Department , Orcid ID: 0009-0001-9941-518X , Mail : gokselkaradeniz0994@hotmail.com**

CURRENT SCIENCE

Barcode: 977266795001

Editors Group:

Concessionaire: Tsisana Kharabadze

Niyaz Bokvadze

Prof. Sabrina Corbi

Prof. Samantha Lewes

""• Current Science Multidisciplinary Academic Journal with

Review Panel is a monthly multidisciplinary academic" ("CURRENT SCIENCE ("Scientific Studies
– Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current

Science Georgia") Science Georgia") journal with a multi-science peer-review." ("Scientific
Studies - Current Science Georgia")

""The journal will be at the subscriber's address in the first week of the month."" ("Scientific
Studies - Current Science Georgia")

- The journal continues to be included in all international rankings and registrations. Quality articles and publications accelerate this ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

""• Response or rejection time for applications varies between 30 and 90 days.""

("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

ABSTRACT

Crisis moments in corporate management are pivotal instances that test the competencies and strategic decision-making abilities of leaders and managers. This research seeks to analyze the impact of proficient leadership and decision-making processes on enterprises during crises. This study, underpinned by a literature analysis and case studies, assesses the role of leaders in crisis management and the influence of decision-making processes on corporate sustainability. The research underscores the significance of strategic thinking, rapid decision-making, and adaptable management strategies during crises, highlighting their crucial role in ensuring the long-term success of the firm and its resilience in overcoming challenges. The significance of leaders' communication, motivation, and guiding abilities in enhancing the efficacy of crisis management procedures during critical situations is also examined. The results provide recommendations for corporate managers to cultivate successful leadership and decision-making strategies amid crises.

Keywords: *Crisis Management, Effective Leadership, Decision Making Processes, Business Sustainability.*

INTRODUCTION

Crises are characterized as unforeseen occurrences that disrupt the regular operations of enterprises and may compel them to fight for their existence. Such scenarios may emerge from abrupt and unforeseen changes in the internal and external settings of enterprises. Numerous variables, including economic swings, natural catastrophes, political instabilities, technical advancements, and escalating rivalry, may precipitate a crisis for firms. Crises need prompt and precise decision-making, proficient leadership abilities, and an evaluation of strategic management procedures. Crisis management is essential for companies to endure and strengthen in the face of catastrophes. Leaders play a crucial role during crises by shaping the business's direction and maintaining staff morale. Effective leadership encompasses situational awareness, strategic thinking in crisis management, communication skills, adaptability to change, and empathy. In crisis circumstances, leaders must cultivate trust among internal and external stakeholders while managing relationships in an atmosphere of uncertainty. The choices made throughout this process not only facilitate crisis resolution but also directly influence the long-term performance and sustainability objectives of the enterprise. Consequently, the strategies used by leaders during crises and their impact on corporate performance need further investigation. This research aimed to underscore the significance of proficient leadership and decision-making procedures during crises. This analysis will investigate the strategic thinking of leaders during crises, the decision-making methods used, and the resultant impacts on firms, drawing on current research and real-world examples. The discussion will focus on the impact of executives' performance during crises on the subsequent strength or weakness of the firm. Furthermore, the strategic instruments and methodologies used by leaders to enhance the efficacy of decision-making processes throughout this phase will

CURRENT SCIENCE

be examined. An additional significant subject of the study is the dynamics of decision-making processes during crises. Decisions made during crises are often conducted under situations of restricted knowledge, elevated stress, and ambiguity. This circumstance necessitates a departure from conventional methodologies and demands rapid, imaginative, and adaptable strategies. The research will examine how the decision-making process is influenced during crises, the elements that impact this process, and the strategic methods firms should use in crisis management. Crisis management not only allows organizations to navigate existing crises but also enhances their resilience to potential future disasters. In this setting, strong leadership and sound decision-making procedures are fundamental components of crisis management. This research seeks to provide insightful conclusions on enhancing corporate performance during crises by thoroughly evaluating these two essential factors.

AIM

This research aims to thoroughly investigate the impact of competent leadership and decision-making processes in company management during crises on business performance and sustainability. Crises have become unavoidable in the contemporary, fast evolving, and unpredictable corporate environment. Effective leadership and strategic decision-making abilities are crucial in crisis management for firms to effectively navigate hard moments. This research seeks to examine the fundamental components of crisis management, the pivotal responsibilities of leaders in these processes, and the impact of their actions on the short- and long-term performance of enterprises. The primary objective of the research is to elucidate the attitudes leaders display in times of crisis, identify the most successful leadership styles, and examine the strategic tactics leaders use during these situations. The management abilities shown by executives during crises are crucial not only for resolving the immediate situation but

CURRENT SCIENCE

also for ensuring the future viability of the organization. The research will thoroughly examine the impact of leadership behaviors and styles in crisis management on corporate success. This analysis will thoroughly explore the choices made by leaders during crises, the formulation of these decisions, and the effectiveness of various leadership styles in crisis management. The secondary objective of the research is to examine the functioning of decision-making processes during crises and to identify strategic approaches that might enhance their efficacy. Crisis situations are characterized by heightened ambiguity and complexity, which directly impacts decision-making processes. The research will examine the adequacy of conventional decision-making systems during crises, the need for rapid and adaptable decision-making, and the challenges faced in this process. The discussion will also include the strategic nature of leaders' actions during crises, their impact on the company, and their role in facilitating recovery and resilience post-crisis. This research also aims to assess the long-term impacts of crisis management techniques on corporate sustainability. Crisis situations provide risks to enterprises, however they also offer opportunities for strategic change and innovation. Crisis management techniques should extend beyond only resolving the crisis; they must also facilitate the attainment of long-term company objectives and the preservation of competitive advantage. This research seeks to elucidate the impact of leadership roles and decision-making systems in crisis management on corporate sustainability.

METHOD

Literature on crisis management, successful leadership, and decision-making processes. The literature review seeks to do a thorough and critical analysis of leadership behaviors, decision-making processes, and their impact on company performance in crisis situations, aligning with the primary objective of the research. This analysis will thoroughly investigate secondary

CURRENT SCIENCE

materials, including academic papers, books, articles, and reports pertaining to crisis management theories, leadership styles, and decision-making models. The crisis management literature will be analyzed to provide a complete knowledge base about the impact of crises on firms, the challenges faced during such periods, and the strategies used to address these challenges. This method will analyze fundamental ideas, theories, and models pertinent to crisis management, while also highlighting the responsibilities of leaders in crisis management and strategic decision-making procedures. The insights derived from crisis management literature will provide a foundation for comprehending successful leadership methods during crises. The literature study on leadership will examine successful leadership styles in crisis situations and their impact on company management. This analysis will concentrate on leadership styles, including transformational, situational, and autocratic leadership, and their efficacy in crisis management. This literature on leadership theories and models will be used to comprehend the leadership techniques adopted by leaders during crises and the impact of these approaches on corporate performance. The literature evaluation on decision-making processes will assess the decision-making mechanisms used by leaders during crises and the efficacy of these procedures. Theories of decision-making, research on the rapidity of strategic choices during crises, and their impact on firms will be examined. Furthermore, the examination will include the management of ambiguity, stress, and time constraint in decision-making processes, as well as their impact on decision quality.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The Concept of Crisis

The notion of crisis is elucidated via several definitions in the social sciences, complicating the establishment of a singular widely acknowledged definition. The term "crisis" is etymologically

derived from the Greek word *krisis*, which signifies "to separate" (Pira and Sohodol, 2010, p. 23). In Chinese, the phrase for crisis is comprised of two distinct characters: *weixiân* (risk) and *jihui* (opportunity), together forming *wěiji* (Okay and Tamam 2014, p. 352). These symbols indicate that a crisis has both advantageous and detrimental elements, encapsulating the concepts of 'opportunity' and 'risk.' The primary characteristic of a crisis—whether it manifests as an opportunity or a threat—primarily hinges on the efficacy of the organization's management in addressing the circumstance (Pira and Sohodol, 2010, p. 23). This notion suggests that a crisis might provide possibilities for growth and development rather than just resulting in devastation. The Oxford Learner's Dictionary describes a crisis as "a period of significant peril, challenge, or uncertainty during which issues must be addressed or critical decisions must be rendered." The term "crisis," derived from the French word "crise," is described in the Turkish Language Association's Great Turkish Dictionary as "a challenging period, downturn, or distress experienced by a society, organization, or individual." Various definitions provided by scholars, researchers, and authors seek to enhance the comprehension and administration of crises prior to, during, or after to their occurrence. Consequently, different viewpoints on the notion of crisis provide distinct meanings. Furthermore, other definitions from diverse domains might be highlighted. Shrivastava (1987, p. 194) characterizes a crisis as "a low-probability, high-consequence event that may jeopardize organizational legitimacy, profitability, and viability." Reid (2000, p. 17) defines a crisis as "any event that may attract negative attention to a company and adversely affect its financial condition, relationships with its target audience, or market reputation." Kernisky (1997, p. 843) characterizes it as an organizational occurrence that significantly impacts the organization and its interconnected parts. A crisis, often seen as an unforeseen occurrence, may threaten an organization's financial

health, reputation, and operational continuity. A crisis may inflict economic, emotional, and physical damage on stakeholders external to the business, such as workers, shareholders, suppliers, and consumers (Coombs 2007, p. 164). A crisis is defined as an unplanned occurrence for swift response, which challenges an organization's current preventative and adaptation strategies, jeopardizing its objectives, values, and assumptions (Dinçer 2003, p. 407). Regester (1989, p. 159) characterizes a crisis as "an event that captures the interest of the media and external entities with a vested interest in an organization's activities, including shareholders, politicians, unions, and environmental advocacy groups." A crisis is often seen as a situation necessitating an urgent and resolute reaction from the organization (Cornelissen 2019, p. 268). Heath and Millar (2004, p. 4) characterize a crisis as an inopportune and often foreseeable occurrence that has substantial immediate and prospective implications for the reputation of the business and its stakeholders. Pensore (2000) contends that every crisis intrinsically encompasses both risks and opportunity. Weick (1988, p. 305) characterizes crises as "low-probability/high-consequence events that jeopardize the fundamental objectives of an organization." Coombs (2000) asserts that crisis encompasses several disciplines, including crisis management, public relations, organizational psychology, management, and rhetoric; the challenge of defining crisis stems from its multidisciplinary characteristics. Mitroff (2000, p. 34) contends that predicting the specifics of a crisis—its occurrence, timing, or causation—is almost impossible. He emphasizes this challenge by asserting that formulating a clear and universal definition is similarly arduous.

Characteristics of the Crisis

As outlined in the "Concept of Crisis" section, although a globally agreed definition of crisis is lacking, uncertainty inherently arises from the unpredictability of outcomes, impacting all

levels from top management to workers and stakeholders inside the business. It is underscored that, when handled adeptly, a crisis might provide chances rather than just adverse outcomes. Crisis moments can generate a complicated organizational environment, necessitating the presence of accountable persons. The essential collaboration and cohesion among people or departments during such periods provide the foundation for the organization to attain its overarching objectives (Avanzi et al., 2017, p. 30). Consequently, crises have some shared traits. Telg (2019, p. 3) delineates these prevalent features as follows: Crises might engender skepticism over the organization's credibility in the public's perception. They may also result in erroneous or skewed views, often including assertions that provide just a partial narrative, so fostering a detrimental public image of the company. Consequently, companies must be equipped to rectify these misconceptions. Crises may severely impact businesses and can arise suddenly, forcing them into a reactive stance to address the crisis, rumors, remarks, and even antagonistic perspectives. Crises often result in a loss of control. A swift and effective reaction to the crisis is essential to dispel this notion. Prompt and efficient response during a crisis demonstrates to the public that the institution is equipped to handle similar occurrences. Pira and Sohodol (2010, p. 27) assert that the attributes of a crisis stem from both environmental and institutional influences. These encompass the peril to the organization's essential objectives and potential existence, the insufficiency of the organization's preventive and anticipatory systems, the imperative for immediate action under time constraints, the element of astonishment induced by unforeseen and abrupt alterations, the discord among decision-makers, and the consequent anxiety and turmoil. Crises are challenging events that signify pivotal moments that may jeopardize an organization's reputation, personnel, financial integrity, or natural resources. They may influence the whole system or its subsystems both mentally and physically, impacting

present or future operations. The ongoing changes seen throughout the crisis may signify a crucial turning point (Lesly, 1991, p. 23). The four fundamental features of crises necessitating particular consideration are: escalating uncertainty within organizations, time constraints, threats, and unexpectedness (Pira and Sohodol, 2010, p. 26). The uncertainty arising during a crisis may impact all individuals inside the business, from senior management to staff members. Consequently, it is recommended that the synchronized and suitable endeavors of various units to address uncertainty, time constraints, dangers, and unforeseen events during a crisis may transform a crisis into an opportunity.

Uncertainty

A crisis may be characterized as an exceptional period for organizations according to its definition. During such periods, the apprehension shown by organizational leaders in response to unfolding events is often mirrored in employee behavior. A crisis engenders a bleak atmosphere inside the business, resulting in significant ambiguity on the trajectory that both the firm and its people need to pursue. This ambiguity persists until the crisis is managed, resulting in interruptions owing to the stress it generates (Pira and Sohodol, 2010, p.26). The uncertainty that arises during crises adversely impacts both managers and workers. The "uncertainty" characteristic of a crisis is one of its most defining and formidable elements. In crisis management, uncertainty denotes the absence of predictability and the challenges associated with forecasting potential outcomes during a crisis. This intrinsic unpredictability undermines the standard operations of an organization, impedes the capacity to make educated judgments, and hinders strategic planning. During crises, established protocols and standard operating procedures can prove insufficient or obsolete, leading to a condition where typical clarity and order give way to confusion and ambiguity. This ambiguity is both a source of stress and a

substantial impediment to successful crisis management, since it obstructs the organization's capacity to react swiftly and efficiently to emergent difficulties. Uncertainty during a crisis mostly originates from the breakdown of communication routes and information flows. Typically, companies depend on established communication methods to disseminate information, make decisions, and coordinate activities. Nevertheless, in times of crisis, these mechanisms may be undermined, resulting in disinformation, delays, and perhaps a total collapse of communication. The resultant ambiguity may engender confusion among workers and stakeholders, since they may be unclear about the appropriate steps to do, whom to trust, or which information is reliable.

The absence of clear and trustworthy information exacerbates the challenges of crisis management, since judgments often rely on incomplete or rapidly evolving data. The uncertainty inherent in a crisis profoundly affects the psychological well-being of people inside an organization. It may result in adverse emotional responses, such as worry, anxiety, frustration, tension, and a feeling of powerlessness stemming from uncertainty about the future. This ambiguity imposes extra strain on leaders and managers, who are expected to direct their teams and make pivotal choices in the absence of clarity. The pressure to succeed under these circumstances may result in burnout, suboptimal decision-making, and a decline in overall organizational morale. Uncertainty among workers may result in less faith in leadership, decreased productivity, and disengagement, hence exacerbating the organization's capacity to handle a crisis successfully.

Time Pressure

A distinguishing aspect of a crisis is the strain of time. In crisis scenarios, temporal constraints significantly influence the progression of events. This pressure is characterized by the urgency

CURRENT SCIENCE

and limitations experienced from the onset of the crisis to the point at which a choice is required. In contrast to standard times when choices may be deliberated and scrutinized thoroughly, emergencies need immediate action and swift execution. Decision-makers often must make judgments without the benefit of comprehensive analysis, thorough study, or significant communication with their teams. Managers must not only make swift judgments but also fulfill their obligations within a constrained timeframe (Pira and Sohodol, 2010, p. 26). This underscores that amid a crisis, it is crucial to make correct judgments that are also timely and suitable for the organization's circumstances. The essence of time pressure during a crisis emphasizes the need of competent management, since the crisis's outcome—whether it transforms into an opportunity or a threat—largely hinges on the handling of time limitations. Time pressure denotes the pressing need for swift decision-making and action that often accompanies such circumstances. Crises often arise abruptly and intensify swiftly, imposing significant limitations on the available reaction time. This urgency necessitates that organizations respond swiftly to alleviate the immediate effects of a crisis, avert future decline, and attend to the concerns of diverse stakeholders. The condensed timeline for decision-making may impose heightened stress and strain on organizational leaders, who must reconcile the need for prompt action with the requirement for comprehensive study and review. Time constraints during a crisis may also exert pressure on organizational resources and decision-making procedures. Organizations with constrained time for option evaluation and solution implementation may have difficulties in coordinating activities, using resources effectively, and sustaining open communication. The need to react effectively may result in impulsive actions that lack thorough consideration, perhaps causing unforeseen repercussions or exacerbating the problem. Effectively managing time pressure necessitates that businesses formulate and execute

comprehensive crisis management strategies, optimize decision-making procedures, and equip essential staff to navigate high-pressure scenarios with poise and efficiency.

Surprise and Threat

The abrupt and unforeseen emergence of a crisis generates considerable strain inside organizations, impacting both senior management and staff. This friction may hinder operations and present significant risks to the institution's stability and objectives. The hazard emerges when the institution's previously established high-level objectives may be susceptible to disturbances caused by the crisis scenario. A crisis may undermine the foundational framework of an institution, including its operations and objectives. The magnitude of this danger may fluctuate based on the characteristics and development of the crisis, the institution's present condition, and the target audience's perception of the situation. The severity influences the actions used in reaction to the crisis, its progression, and its ultimate conclusion (Pira and Sohodol, 2010, p. 26). A crisis is seen as a danger mostly due to its disruption of standard operations and the resultant significant anxiety. Surprises during a crisis include abrupt, unforeseen alterations that impede the operation of the organization. The failure of decision-makers and managers to identify and respond to the crisis might heighten the element of surprise. These surprises mostly result from deficiencies in environmental assessment, information collection and processing, and the maintenance of efficient reporting systems (Pira and Sohodol, 2010, p. 27). Deficiencies in information collection and decision-making often arise from insufficient experience and preparation. Organizations are caught off guard by crises when they neglect to identify early warning indicators of adverse changes in their surroundings. This failure is directly linked to insufficient information collection and lack of experience (Dinçer, 2003, p. 410). Seitel (2016, pp. 353-354) identifies six prevalent features that indicate

CURRENT SCIENCE

the onset of a crisis and are often seen as unchangeable. Crises often arise suddenly, whether from natural catastrophes (such as hurricanes) or human-induced incidents (such as theft or fraud). Organizations often become aware of these incidents when media and public relations experts inquire about reaction strategies. Secondly, amid a crisis, information becomes disjointed and excessive. Rumors spread, social media accentuate misinformation, and news agencies need precise updates, complicating the management of information flow. Third, as the crisis progresses, the intensity of events escalates, with financial markets and the public seeking clarity, so complicating information management further. Fourth, external scrutiny increases as media outlets, financial experts, and the public propagate rumors and demand solutions, therefore exacerbating the agency's difficulties in crisis management.

Causes of the Crisis

Comprehending and preparing for impending crises takes more than only acknowledging that crises arise suddenly. Pauchant and Mitroff (1992, p. 15) characterize a crisis as "a disruption that physically impacts a system in its entirety and jeopardizes its fundamental assumptions, subjective identity, and existential essence." They advocate for a dynamic viewpoint on crises, categorizing them into phases including "incident," "accident," "conflict," and "crisis." This continuum underscores that crises are heterogeneous; each crisis evolves uniquely and necessitates distinct conceptual frameworks and management tactics. (Massey & Larsen, 2006, p. 67). According to Black (1993, p. 139), possible crises are categorized into two types: awareness of unknowns and unawareness of unknowns. Examples of the first group include coal mines, nuclear plants, and transportation networks where the dangers are well understood, although the timing of the incidents remains unpredictable. The second group encompasses occurrences when the timing of natural catastrophes is almost difficult to forecast, including

CURRENT SCIENCE

volcanic eruptions, floods, and earthquakes. Numerous variables precipitate crises inside institutions, including inability to adjust to environmental changes, communication breakdowns, insufficient training, and coordination deficiencies. Certain elements may provide considerable hazards and may result in substantial issues for the institution, however others are more severe (Pira and Sohodol, 2019, p. 27). The relationship between an institution and its surroundings may also result in crises. External demands and expectations that surpass an institution's resources and skills, or an environment that fails to satisfy the institution's requirements, may interrupt regular operations and precipitate a crisis (Dinçer, 1998, p. 385). Harwati (2013) categorizes crises into two primary types: i. Natural crises arise from unforeseen catastrophes such as epidemics, earthquakes, and storms; ii. Human-induced crises originate from neglect, insufficient training, and deliberate or inadvertent mistakes. Natural crises are often unforeseen, but man-made crises tend to be more foreseeable and may significantly harm an organization's image and financial stability if not promptly handled.

Figure 1. *The Concept of Crisis (Tüz , 2001: 4)*

Concept of Business Management

The notion of business management includes the strategic and operational procedures of planning, organizing, directing, and regulating resources to attain organizational objectives. The fundamental objective of business management is to optimize efficiency and effectiveness within a company. It entails the orchestration of human, financial, and informational resources to achieve intended outcomes, guaranteeing the efficient and effective operation of a company. Effective management is essential for the success and longevity of any firm, since it synthesizes many roles and strategies that correspond with the organization's objectives. Business management fundamentally comprises four core functions: planning, organizing, leading, and controlling. Planning entails establishing objectives and identifying the most effective strategy to attain those objectives. It necessitates that managers forecast future circumstances, establish priorities, and formulate plans to tackle prospective issues. The second function, organizing, emphasizes the systematic arrangement of resources and activities to efficiently execute plans. This entails delineating roles, duties, and establishing a structure inside the business to facilitate effective workflow. The third function, leadership, pertains to encouraging and directing personnel to attain the organization's objectives. Effective leadership encompasses guiding and influencing colleagues while cultivating a good work environment that promotes productivity and engagement. Leaders must communicate effectively, provide assistance, and motivate their colleagues to excel. Effective leadership is essential for sustaining organizational morale and enhancing performance (Stokes and Wilson, 2010). The ultimate role of business management, control, is overseeing and assessing the organization's performance to guarantee the achievement of objectives. This procedure involves establishing performance benchmarks,

assessing actual performance, and executing remedial measures as required. Control guarantees that the organization remains aligned and adjusts to changes in both internal and external settings. It encompasses both quantitative and qualitative evaluations to provide a holistic perspective on organizational performance. Alongside these fundamental duties, contemporary company management increasingly prioritizes strategic management, including long-term planning and competitive positioning. Strategic management emphasizes the identification of market opportunities and challenges, evaluation of internal capabilities, and formulation of plans to attain competitive advantage. This facet of company management incorporates components like market analysis, competitive strategy, and resource allocation to guarantee that the corporation stays flexible and robust in a changing commercial landscape. The notion of business management is complicated and dynamic, mirroring the intricacies of organizational management in today's competitive and fast-evolving environment. Attaining organizational success and sustainability requires a combination of strategic vision, operational efficiency, and proficient leadership (Tüz, 2001).

The Concept of Leadership

The notion of leadership is complex and essential for directing companies toward their objectives and cultivating a productive atmosphere. Leadership primarily involves influencing, inspiring, and leading people or teams to attain shared objectives. It encompasses more than just managerial tasks; it includes the capacity to inspire, formulate vision, and instigate change within an organization. Effective leadership is defined by a profound comprehension of both the strategic and interpersonal aspects of guiding individuals and overseeing processes. Leadership fundamentally entails establishing a vision and direction for an organization or team. A leader conveys a distinct and persuasive vision that aligns with the organization's

CURRENT SCIENCE

objectives and inspires others to adopt and strive for that vision (Minkes et al., 1999). This entails formulating a strategic plan and successfully conveying it to ensure comprehensive understanding and commitment to the proposed direction. Visionary leaders excel at anticipating future possibilities and navigating their teams through uncertainty and transformation; they foster an atmosphere that promotes innovation and advancement. A crucial element of leadership is the capacity to encourage and inspire people. Effective leaders cultivate the trust and respect essential for nurturing a healthy and productive work environment among their teams. They use several motivating strategies, including acknowledging accomplishments, offering constructive criticism, and establishing hard but attainable objectives. By comprehending and addressing the wants and aspirations of team members, leaders may enhance engagement and performance, resulting in elevated work satisfaction and organizational commitment. Leadership entails formulating and executing plans to navigate change and surmount obstacles. Leaders must possess proficiency in decision-making, problem-solving, and crisis management. This entails evaluating circumstances, considering alternatives, and making informed decisions that correspond with the organization's objectives. Leaders must exhibit flexibility and adaptability, enabling them to react effectively to changing circumstances and rising challenges. They are essential in managing both anticipated and unforeseen changes, guaranteeing that the business stays adaptable and receptive to internal and exterior conditions. Effective leadership is defined by emotional intelligence, which includes self-awareness, self-regulation, empathy, and social skills. Leaders with elevated emotional intelligence are more adept at understanding and regulating their own emotions as well as those of others (Niaber, 2010). This capability enables them to cultivate robust connections, mediate disagreements, and foster a supportive and collaborative work environment. Emotional

intelligence is essential for creating an inclusive atmosphere in which team members feel appreciated and inspired. Thus, the notion of leadership is fluid and includes many abilities and qualities essential for guiding people and organizations toward their objectives. It include establishing a vision, inspiring and motivating others, managing change, and exhibiting emotional intelligence. Effective leadership encompasses not just managing and regulating but also empowering individuals, cultivating a healthy work atmosphere, and responding to the organization's changing requirements. Consequently, leadership is an essential element of organizational performance and significantly influences the direction and culture of a company (Niaber, 2010).

Stages of Crisis Management

The methodology for crisis management differs based on the characteristics of the problem. Effective crisis management often encompasses many critical steps aimed at minimizing harm and facilitating a return to normalcy with little loss. Can (2002, p. 337) identifies the following stages: i) awareness of crisis signals, ii) preparation and protection, iii) control, iv) restoration to normalcy, and v) learning and assessment. The first phase, acknowledging crisis signals, entails detecting preliminary signs of a possible catastrophe. Managers must be vigilant and attuned to these indications to adeptly navigate the institution through the crisis. Neglecting to monitor and analyze these signals may increase the probability of a comprehensive crisis (Akat et al. 1994, p. 352). Implementing and sustaining an efficient early warning system is crucial at this juncture. The subsequent phase, preparation and protection, emphasizes proactive strategies to alleviate the effects of the crisis. This encompasses comprehending the management philosophy, disseminating fundamental procedures and principles, and strategizing for possible crises (Dinçer, 1995, p. 335). At this level, companies execute plans to safeguard their

CURRENT SCIENCE

stakeholders and objectives from possible threats. Regester and Larkin (2005, pp. 197-198) propose several activities for this phase, such as fostering a constructive attitude towards crisis management, aligning performance with public expectations, cultivating trust, identifying opportunities during the crisis, and recording actions undertaken for accountability. The control phase entails top management implementing decisive measures to address the issue based on the information at hand. Notwithstanding efficient early warning and planning, some situations may nonetheless intensify. In these instances, it is essential for top management to meticulously monitor the situation and modify their tactics as required (Akat et al., 1994, p. 344). This phase emphasizes the administration of the current crisis to mitigate its effects and restore stability. The normalization phase focuses on reestablishing stability and reverting the organization to its pre-crisis condition. During this phase, initiatives are undertaken to eradicate interruptions and restore the organization's operational order. The objective is to adjust the organization to the changing environmental circumstances and mitigate the adverse impacts resulting from the crisis (Akat et al., 1994, p. 344). The learning and evaluation phase include assessing the crisis management approach to discern lessons learnt. This phase entails assessing choices and activities executed during the crisis to enhance future interventions. Tack (1994, pp. 62-63) underscores the need of eliminating impediments to efficiency, rearticulating organizational objectives more effectively, and acknowledging successful solutions used during the crisis. This introspective approach aids companies in enhancing their resilience and readiness for impending disasters.

Figure 2. Stages of Crisis Management (Can, 2005: 398)

Leadership in Times of Crisis

Leadership during crises is an essential aspect of good company management, since it entails steering an organization through substantial uncertainty and upheaval. During such periods, leaders must exhibit remarkable adaptability, decisiveness, and communication proficiency to manage the intricacies of the circumstances and maintain stability. Effective crisis leadership encompasses not just addressing immediate difficulties but also equipping the company for sustained recovery and adaptability. Providing clear guidance and sustaining morale under duress is crucial for the company to operate and eventually prosper despite difficult situations. A crucial element of leadership in a crisis is the ability to make rapid and informed judgments. During crises, decision-making processes are often expedited owing to the urgency of the circumstances (Tack, 1994). Leaders must evaluate available information, assess the possible risks and rewards of different actions, and make prompt choices along with the organization's strategic objectives. Leaders must manage the intricacies of a crisis under time constraints and maybe little information, necessitating a combination of analytical abilities and intuitive

CURRENT SCIENCE

discernment. The efficacy of these choices is vital for mitigating the crisis's effects and steering the organization towards recovery. Moreover, proficient crisis leadership entails fostering a feeling of cohesion and resilience inside the business. Leaders must engage in open communication with workers and stakeholders, delivering timely information and assuring them of the measures taken to mitigate the situation. This communication is essential for preserving trust and alleviating worker worry, so facilitating operational continuity and productivity. Leaders must possess the ability to manage stress and maintain a positive perspective, as their demeanor may profoundly influence the corporate atmosphere and the capacity of workers to stay focused and motivated throughout difficult periods. Leaders may facilitate companies' successful and resilient recovery from a crisis by exhibiting empathy, offering assistance, and cultivating a collaborative atmosphere (Akat et al. 1999).

Decision Making Processes in Times of Crisis

Decision-making processes during crises are more arduous owing to heightened pressure, ambiguity, and the rapid progression of events. In contrast to standard decision-making, which often involves extended study and contemplation, crisis decision-making demands swift action and flexibility. Effectively making choices in high-stress circumstances is essential for mitigating the crisis's effects and guiding the business toward recovery and stability. A critical aspect of crisis decision-making is the need for rapid response. Crises often arise unexpectedly, requiring prompt action from leaders to address imminent dangers and mitigate harm. The decision-making process under these settings often entails a compressed timetable, necessitating judgments to be made with little knowledge and under significant pressure. Leaders must prioritize essential concerns, often guided by their expertise, intuition, and available facts, to make prompt, educated decisions (Tack, 1994). This urgency may necessitate

CURRENT SCIENCE

trade-offs between conflicting goals, balancing immediate reactions with long-term strategic concerns. A crucial element of decision-making during a crisis is the management of ambiguity and risk. In a crisis, the environment is marked by elevated uncertainty and volatility, complicating the accurate prediction of events. Decision-makers must evaluate risks and possible consequences while navigating the uncertainties inherent in the situation. This entails collecting and scrutinizing pertinent information, assessing prospective situations, and contemplating the ramifications of various courses of action. Efficient decision-making in these circumstances often depends on scenario planning and risk assessment methods to foresee probable obstacles and ready oneself for diverse possibilities. Communication is essential in the decision-making process during a crisis. Leaders must guarantee that their choices are conveyed clearly and effectively to all stakeholders, including workers, customers, and partners. Clear communication facilitates expectation management, fosters trust, and ensures alignment among all stakeholders with the organization's response approach. Coordinating efforts and ensuring that all organizational components are aligned towards shared objectives is also crucial (Tack, 1994). Effective communication may reduce misunderstanding and opposition, so enabling more seamless execution of crisis choices. The engagement of essential stakeholders and the use of collaborative strategies may enhance decision-making in a crisis. Involving a varied array of stakeholders, such as subject matter experts and frontline personnel, may provide significant ideas and views that enhance decision-making quality. Collaborative decision-making facilitates the distribution of responsibility and burden by using the team's combined skills and experience. By cultivating a collaborative atmosphere, executives may improve the organization's capacity to react effectively to crises and adapt to changing circumstances.

CONCLUSION

Employed the literature review approach to examine the essential aspects of crisis management, emphasizing effective leadership and decision-making processes during crises. The literature research offered an extensive insight into organizational crisis management and the essential traits that lead to favorable results. A comprehensive examination of scientific literature, theoretical frameworks, and empirical research revealed significant insights into the roles of leadership and decision-making in crisis situations. Effective leadership in crises is characterized by the capacity to provide clear guidance, cultivate resilience among team members, and sustain attention on both immediate and strategic objectives. Leaders proficient in these domains may navigate their businesses through tumultuous periods by using their abilities to foster trust and mitigate uncertainty. Literature indicates that such leaders often demonstrate decisiveness, emotional intelligence, and flexibility, traits essential for navigating businesses through the complex problems presented by crises. The decision-making process during crises is marked by haste and complexity. The literature assessment indicates that effective decision-making in emergencies needs a combination of expertise, swift information processing, and strategic vision. Effective decision-makers are persons capable of synthesizing limited information, evaluating risks, and executing prompt actions while reconciling short-term needs with long-term objectives. The incorporation of many viewpoints and cooperative methods enhances the quality of judgments under high-pressure situations. Literature findings underscore the significance of leadership and decision-making in the successful management of emergencies. Organizations that excel in these domains are better equipped to alleviate the adverse effects of crises and leverage possible growth and recovery possibilities. The literature

review process enabled an extensive examination of these topics and offered significant insights into how organizations might plan for and react to crises to guarantee their sustainability and resilience. The literature assessment indicates that the interplay between leadership and decision-making is essential for effective crisis management. This study elucidates the essential characteristics and mechanisms that facilitate successful crisis response, based on known theories and empirical data. Future study in this domain may further investigate the changing dynamics of crisis management and the implementation of these principles across many organizational environments.

RESOURCES

- Avanzi , D.S. , Foggiatto , A., Anderson , S., Santos , V.A., Deschamps , F., Loures , E., & Fretias , R. (2017). A framework for interoperability assessment in crisis management . *Journal of Industrial Information*, 5, 26-38.
- Akat, İ ., Budak, G., & Budak, G. (1994). *Business Management* (1st ed.). Beta Printing Publishing Distribution Inc.
- Black, S. (1993). *The essentials of public relations* . Kogan Page Ltd.
- Combs , T. W. (2012). *Ongoing Crisis communication : Planning, managing , and responding* . Sage Publications.
- Cornelissen , J. (2019). *Corporate Communication* (Ç. S. Bir & İ. Suher , Trans.). The Kitap Publishing House.
- Dinçer, Ö. (2003). *Strategic management and business policy* (6th ed.). Beta Printing.

- Lesly , P. (1991). Lesly's handbook of public relations and communications . Probus Publishing Company .
- Mitroff , II (2000). Managing crises before they happen : What every executive and manager needs to know about Crisis management .AMACOM.
- Nienaber , H. (2010). Conceptualization of management and leadership Management Decision , 48(5), 661-675.
- Minkes , A. L ., Small, M. W., & Chatterjee , S. R. (1999). Leadership and bussines ethics : Does it matter ? Implications for management . Journal of Business Ethics , 20(4), 327-335.
- Okay, A. , & Okay, A. (2014). Public relations concepts, strategies and applications (7th ed.). DER Publications.
- Pauchant , T. C ., & Mitroff , II (1992). transforming the crisis-prone organization . Jossey-Bass Publishers .
- Pira , A. , & Sohodol , Ç. (2010). Crisis management: an evaluation from the perspective of public relations (3rd ed.). Communication Publishing.
- Regester , M. (1989). Crisis Management : How to turn into a crisis into an opportunity . Hutchinson Business.
- Reid , J. (2000). Crisis management : Planning and media relations for the design and construction industry . Wiley .
- Seitel , FP (2016). The practice of public relations (S. Mengü, Trans.). Nobel Publications.
- Shrivastava , P. (1987). Strategic management : Concepts and practices . South Western.
- Stokes , D ., & Wilson, N. (2010). small business management and entrepreneurship Cengage Learning EMEA.
- Tack , PB (1994). Management in times of crisis (Y. Güneri, Trans.). Related Publishing.

Tuz , MV (2001). Crisis business management. Alfa Publishing House.

ABOUT THE AUTHOR

Göksel KARADENİZ

Goksel Karadeniz, is a PhD student in Business Administration at St. Clements University. He completed her BA in Business Administration at Anadolu University. He then completed her MA in Economics and Finance at Muğla Sıtkı Koçman University. He is currently working as an Administrative Affairs Specialist at Acıbadem Bodrum Hospital. He can be reached at gokselkaradeniz0994@gmail.com

Dr. Pamir DIRIL

**Dr. Pamir Diril is a lecturer in the Turkish Department at St. Clements University. Pamir Diril graduated from the Department of Psychology. Pamir Diril completed his MA in the Department of Clinical Psychology with his thesis titled “Cognitive Behavioral Therapy for Cognitive Impairment in Schizophrenia” and his completed thesis title is “Psychological and sociological effects of domestic violence” at St. Clements University Department of Clinical Psychology. Dr. Pamir Diril has scientific articles in many international and national refereed journals. Dr. Diril is currently She works in the Department of Psychology at Clements University.

